

The development and extinction of Jainism in Ancient North Bengal

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Abstract:

Different religions have been living in India since ancient times. From the sixth century BC onwards, Buddhism, Jainism, Vaisnavism, and Saivism were the dominant religions. All these religions were established as a protest movement against the Brahmanical religion. These religions spread to different parts of India. Among these Buddhism and Jainism also spread in the then Bengal. However, in this article, I will discuss the impact of Jainism on the northern part of Bengal. Jainism had spread deeply in Bengal till the seventh century, i.e. the reign of Pala and Sen. Later, as a result of Muslim invasions in North Bengal, the religion gradually became extinct. So my discussion will continue until the seventh century.

Keywords: Jainism, North Bengal

At the beginning of the article, I will define the boundaries of the discussion. We will first discuss what is meant by 'North Bengal' in ancient times. We know that in ancient times there was no state or district or pargana called 'North Bengal'. Generally, in the late nineteenth century, we get the name 'North Bengal'. However, the region of North Bengal was known by a few names in ancient times. We generally know the northern part of the Ganga-Padma River in undivided Bengal, commonly known as 'North Bengal'. Dinajpur, Rajshahi, Pabna, Bogra, Malda, Rangpur, Jalpaiguri, and Darjeeling - these eight districts made up North Bengal. Most of the first six districts covered most of the ancient *Pundravardhana bhukti*, and some parts of north-eastern India, Jalpaiguri and Darjeeling districts, consisting of Kamrup kingdom or *Pragjyotishbhukti*.¹

Jainism in general is a doctrine of protest against Vedic philosophy. Jainism was propagated when the people were looking for a way out of the Vedic age due to the pressure of rituals and caste. According to Historian Ram Sharan Sharma says that "*Jainism made first serious attempt to mitigate the evils of the varna order and the ritualistic Vedic religion. The early Jainas discarded Sanskrit language mainly patronized by the brahmanas. They adopted Prakrit language of the common people to preach their doctrines.*"² According to the Jain tradition, 24th Tirthankars have developed Jainism. According to the *Bhagwat Purana* and *Vishnu Purana*, Rishabh Nath was the first Tirthankara of this religion in ancient times. The names of three Tirthankaras are found in the *Jajurveda*, namely Rishabh, Ajit, and Aristhanemi. According to the Jains text, the 22nd Tirthankara Neminath was a contemporary of Lord Krishna and a member of the *Jadu* dynasty. The Jains are believed to have been strong during the 23rd Tirthankara **Parsvanath** in the sixth century BC. Mahavira was the last Tirthankara. The qualitative change of Jainism was achieved mainly by **Parsvanath** and Mahavira. However, they never claimed that they had established any new religion.³

Mahavira has also shed more light on the sorrows of human life. It is said in the *Acharanga Sutra* that the world of this living being is involved, miserable where teaching is difficult and irrational. In this miserable world, ignorant people have suffered and caused misery by various deeds. The Jain Agamas enumerate five *vratas* (vows) which ascetics and householders must observe. These ethical principles were preached by Mahavira:- (1)

Ahimsa (Non-violence or non-injury): Mahavira taught that every living being has sanctity and dignity which should be respected as one expects one's own sanctity and dignity to be respected. **Ahimsa**, Jainism's first and most important vow, applies to actions, speech, and thought. (2) **Satya** (truthfulness): Applies to oneself and others. (3) **Asteya** (non-stealing): Not taking anything that has not been given. (4) **Brahmacharya** (chastity): Abstinence from sex and sensual pleasures for monks, and faithfulness to one's partner for householders (5) **Aparigraha** (non-attachment): For lay people, an attitude of non-attachment to property or worldly possessions; for mendicants, not owning anything.⁴

Jainism is atheistic. This belief has nothing to do with the existence of God. According to this doctrine, the activities of the universe are being regulated by an eternal law and the cosmic waves of endless rise and fall are coming and going. There is a soul in everything in the world. The purpose of life is to sanctify the soul. Jains believe that the soul will become pure in a harmonious way of life. Mahavira thought that only a monk could lead such a life. He also thinks that a person's rebirth depends on the deeds of his pre-birth. That is, if a person has done good deeds in the previous birth, then he will be born in a higher caste. According to Ram Sharan Sharma says that “*Jainism mainly aims at the attainment of freedom from worldly bonds. It is not necessary to use any ritual for acquiring such liberation. It can be obtained through full knowledge and action. Full knowledge, action and liberation are considered to be the three gems or ratnas of Jainism.*”⁵ Nine basic theories are accepted in this religion. They are *Jiva, Ajib, Punya, Paap, Ashrab, Sambar, Bandhu, Nirjara and Moksha*.

Jains worship different types of deities as symbols of different qualities. They worshiped the idols of 24th Tirthankaras. Not only did they worship them, but they also worshiped Hindu gods and goddesses like *Lakshmi, Ganesh, Kubera*, etc. Each Tirthankara had a symbol. For example, Adinath's symbol was bull and Mahavira's symbol was lion. Besides, each of them had a god of worship and rule. They are mentioned in Jain scriptures as *Jaksha* and *Jakshini*. The Jains valued education very much. According to their tradition, the number of these goddesses was twelve and *Saraswati* was at the top of them. To the Jains, he was a deity. He used to conduct the work of propagating the religion of Tirthankaras.⁶

I have already mentioned that the promoters of Jainism were twenty-four Tirthankaras. Most of these 24th Tirthankaras appeared and settled in present-day Bihar. The last and foremost Jain Tirthankara Mahavira was born in the *Kshatriya Jnatrika* clan of *Kundagrama (Kundalpur)* near *Vaisali* in northern Bihar. This *Kundagrama* or *Kundalpur* belongs to Mazaffarpur district, the present name is *Basukunda*. His *Nirvana* period was in the sixth century BC. It is only natural that the influence of these missionaries from Bihar should spread to neighboring Bengal. In ancient times the political, social, and cultural relations of North Bengal with North Bihar were very close.⁷

According to the Jain scripture *Acharanga Sutra*, Mahavira himself came in the sixth century BC to preach Jainism in *Rarh, Bajaj Bhumij, Subang Bhumij*. Prior to Mahavira, the main pilgrimage site of Jain Tirthankaras like Neminath and Parsvanath was *Pareshnath* hill in Bengal. According to Jain mythology, Mahavira was also associated with *Manbhum, Singbhum*, and *Burdwan*. According to the Jain scripture *Acharanga Sutra*, when he went to those countries, the people of that country attacked Mahavira and threw dogs at him with a snarl. The most important thing is that according to the *Acharanga Sutra*, when such practices were prevalent in South Bengal (Rarh Region) in the sixth century BC, Jainism had a considerable influence in North Bengal. *Pundravardhana* was then the heart of religion, education, culture. It is known from the *Kalpa Sutra* that at that time *Pundravardhana* i.e. North Bengal was inhabited by a large number of Jains. According to that scripture, there were four special branches of Jains in East India, namely - *Pandvardhanika (Pundravardhana), Khadiya (Khalimpur), Kotivarshiya (Kotivarsha), Tamralittiya (Tamralipta)*. All but four of these four branches were in the heart of North Bengal. It is known from an inscription found in *Paharpur* village of East Dinajpur district (478-469 AD) that there was a huge Jain monastery of *Acharya Guhanandi* in one of the *Vata Gohali*. Later, Maharaja Dharmapala built another *Vihara* at *Somepur* in *Paharpur*. From that

inscription, it is known that a Hindu **Nath Sharma** and his wife **Rami**, donated land for **Jain Vihara** in 478-469 AD. At that time **Padmarath** was the king of **Kotivarsha**.⁸

Jain text **Bhagawati Sutra** has the name of the country. Bengal is mentioned among these sixteen countries. Bengal is the region to the west of the Ganga-Bhagirathi. **Pundra** is the present Rajshahi, Bogra, Dinajpur, Rangpur i.e. the whole northern region. The Jain **Acharanga Sutra** mentions the region of **Rarh**. **Rarh** is divided into northern and southern parts. The boundary of North **Rarh** is marked by natural boundaries by the rivers Ganga Bhagirathi and Ajay. However, it can be generally said that the west bank of Bhagirathi extends to the South Sea, including parts of Murshidabad-Burdwan-Birbhum-Bankura-Hughli-Medinipur. The names and boundaries of these towns were later changed. The first mention of the **Pundra** people is found in **Aitareya Brahman**. In this text, Bishwamitra mentions **Pundras** along with various other tribes living on the border of **Aryavarta**, viz., **Anga, Shabar, Pulinda, and Mutib**. Here **Pundrakom** is called **Dasyukom**.⁹

As I mentioned earlier, there was a king named **Padmarath** in the **Kotivarsha** of many years ago. His queen's name was **Padmashri**. There was a Brahmin named **Some Sharma** under the protection of this king. **Some Sharma's** only son was born in the city of **Kotivarsha**. The son's name is **Bhadrabahu**. The present Gangarampur was the birthplace of **Bhadrabahu**. **Bhadrabahu's** inclination towards education was immense from his childhood. His only job was to do good to the people. Jain acharya **Forth Śruta Kevalīs** Sri **Govardhanacharya** came to the **Kotivarsha** on the occasion of pilgrimage. Seeing the talent of **Bhadrabahu**, **Sri Govardhanacharya** was pleased and initiated him into Jainism. Later, when Sri **Govardhanacharya** died, **Bhadrabahu** was appointed as the leader of Jainism. At this time Chandragupta Maurya, the founder of the Maurya Empire, became a recluse. In this state, Chandragupta took initiation from **Bhadrabahu**. **Bhadrabahu**, the **guru** of the Mauryan emperor Chandragupta, was the **Fifth Śruta Kevalīs**. After the death of Tirthankara Mahavira, his three disciples and a disciple were the only three. **Kevalīs** means knower. They were followed by other **Fifth Śruta Kevalīs**. North Bengal occupies a prominent place in the history of Jainism in India.

It is said that in the Eight century BC, the 23rd **Tirthankara Parsvanath** came to the **Pundranagara** to preach. Then in the sixth century BC, Mahavira came to **Pundravardhana** to preach his religion. But no acceptable evidence of the arrival of these two **Tirthankaras** at **Pundravardhana** has been discovered. It is also said that **Sudharma**, a close disciple of Mahavira, and **Jambusvami**, a disciple of **Sudharma**, came to **Pundravardhana** and preached the scriptures. Both of them were **Kevalīs**. Due to the **tomb of Jambusvami** at **Kotipur**, the city became a Jain pilgrimage site.¹⁰

Towards the end of the reign of Chandragupta, the founder of the Mauryan Empire, there was a severe famine in northern India for 12 years. At this time, when Emperor Chandragupta felt asceticism in his mind, he took initiation in Jainism from **Bhadrabahu**. Grants will not be easy for all Jain monks during the famine. Considering that **Bhadrabahu** went to South India with half of the Jain **Sangha**, that is, 12,000 monks, the other half remained in North India under the leadership of **Acharya Sthulabhadra**. During the famine, these monks in northern India relaxed the rules of the association and were forced to go out to collect alms, so they started wearing white clothes. They are **Svetambaras**. And those who went to South India under the leadership of **Bhadrabahu** became known as **Digambaras**. Chandragupta Maurya went to South India with **Bhadrabahu** and spent his last life in the service of Guru. **Bhadrabahu** died in Mysore (now Karnataka) in the state of **Shravana Belagola**, probably in 297 BC, after propagating and establishing the scriptures in South India. That place has become a Jain pilgrimage site.¹¹

From the stanzas of the **Kalpa Sutra**, we learn that **Bhadrabahu** had four **Thera** disciples - all belonging to the **Kashyapa** clan, **Bhadrabahu** himself being of the 'ancient' clan. These four disciples are **Godas, Agnidatta, Janadatta** and **Somadatta**. From this **Bhadrabahu**-disciple **Godas**, a separate and distinct community was formed within the **Nigrantha** community called **Godas**. Over time, these **Godasas** disciples were divided into four branches - **Pandvardhana (Pundravardhana), Khadiya (Khalimpur), Kotivarshiya (Kotivarsha), Tamralittiya (Tamralipta)**. One by one a branch was formed around a place.

Since it has two branches centered on *Kotivarsha* and *Pundravardhana*, it is very clear that the *Nigrantha* religion was well established in North Bengal at that time. The death of *Bhadrabahu* took place in 297 BC when his disciple *Godas* and the establishment of God's branches took place in the second and first centuries BC. The mention of these branches in the inscriptions of the first century BC and the first century AD proves that the scriptural religion is still well established in the region.¹²

According to historians, towards the end of the Pala period, the Jains merged with the *Abdut community*. Evidence of the existence of Jains of *Kotivarshiya* during the Pala and Sen periods is found through idols. Various Jain idols of Rishabhath, Adinath, Neminath, Shantinath, Parsvanath made in the ninth to twelfth centuries are found in the Dinajpur region. Vaishnavism and Saivism and Vedic Brahmanism have been gaining ground since the Gupta age over *Kotivarsha*, and atheistic Jainism has been losing its popularity. Moreover, Jainism did not get the patronage of the kings and princes here.¹³

In the *Kalpa Sutra* of Bhadrabahu, a Jain writer, *Kotivarsha* has been used as *Kotivarshiya* in the sense of the East Indian Jain community. *Sonitpur* is also mentioned in *Vishnu Purana* and *Srimad Bhagwata*. Not only is there a description of *Kotivarshiya* in the *Vayu Purana* and the *Brihata Sanhita*, but in the *Vayu Purana* it is also called 'Nagar'. The copper plate found from *Damodarpur* in Dinajpur district shows that it has been identified as a district and capital of the district under the province of *Pundravardhana* for *Kotivarsha*. Even during the Pala period, the glory of *Kotivarsha* was intact. In the *Ramcharit* of Sandhyakar Nandi, there is a description of the great splendor of *Sonitpur*.¹⁴

According to the *Bhagwat Sutra*, one of Mahavira's desciple *Gosal*, was the founder of *Ajivik Dharma*, another religious division of the time. Along with Jainism, this non-existent religion gained considerable popularity in North Bengal. It is also known that *Punda King Mahapoum* of that time did a lot for the propagation of this religion. Evidence of the spread of Jainism in *Pundravardhana* in the forth and Third centuries BC is found in the Jain text *Divyavadana*. According to this book, Ashoka once killed 18,000 *Ajivikas* of *Patliputra* for the crime of *Pundravardhana's Nigranthas* (by mistake). Although it is not possible to determine the true nature of this incident, it can be said that there was a considerable spread of Jains here. Kshitimohan Sen, referring to the murder, commented, "At that time, 18,000 *Nigranthas* or *Jains* were found in *Pundravardhana* for the purpose of this murder." Dr. Ramesh Chandra Majumdar in his book "History of Ancient Bengal" published from Calcutta in 1971 mentions the incident in that Ashoka killed 18,000 *Ajivikas* of *Pundravardhana* in one day. Nalini Nath Dasgupta, in his book "Banglay Buddhadharma", narrates the story. Dr. Prabodh Chandra Bagchi writes that Ashoka ordered the killing of all the *Nigranthas* in *Patliputra* Nagar (not *Pundravardhana*). Dr. Nihar Ranjan Roy wrote in his famous book "Bangalir Itihas" that Ashoka once killed 18,000 *Ajivikas* of *Patliputra* for the crime (mistakenly?) of *Pundravardhana's Nigrasthas* (Jains). So these 18,000 *Nigranthas* who were killed were residents of *Patliputra Nagara* or *Pandavardhana*? It is to be noted here that Dr. Ramesh Chandra Majumdar, Dr. Niharranjan Roy, and Nalini Nath Dasgupta have all referred to the "Divyavadana" edited by Cowell and Neil as sources. On the other hand, Dr. Asha Das quotes in his research book "Bangla Sahitya Bouddhadharma O Sanskriti" that 18,000 *Ajivikas* of *Pundravardhana* were killed. However, if the 18,000 *Nigranthas* who were killed were not residents of *Pundravardhana*, the incident reveals that there were not only *Nigrantha* monks in the *Pundravardhana*, but also *Nigrantha* worshipers who could dare to insult Buddha even during Ashoka's reign; that is, there was their majority and dominance. Dr. Ramesh Chandra Majumdar did not find the story of *Divyabadana* very believable, but acknowledged its value as proof of the predominance of Jainism in Bengal and especially in North Bengal during the time of Ashoka.¹⁵

Aryan religion first came to the land of Bangladesh through North Bengal in the second century BC on the basis of Jainism. It is known from a copper plate found on the *Paharpura* that there was a *Jain Vihara* in that place in the fourth century or earlier. According to *Hiuen Tsang*, the number of *Digambaras* Jains in this country was high at that time. But later, when the influence of Jainism diminished, the number of followers of Jainism also decreased.¹⁶

Jain image of the ninth to twelfth centuries are found in Dinajpur, Barind, etc. Jainism spread in the region during this century. In the present Barind region, Seven Jain image have been found as a symbol of the position of Jains, of which five are in the Barind Research Museum in Rajshahi and two in the Dinajpur Museum. All these idols belong to the Pala period. Among the Jain image preserved in the Barind Research Museum are the statues of Shantinath and Rishabhath. There are also rare *yaksha* duets. Jain image are rarely found in the Dinajpur region. Although Jainism had considerable influence in Bengal from the second century BC to the seventh century AD, I do not know of any Jain idol found here before the seventh century. Statues of Tirthankara Rishabhath and Parsvanath have been found in the Dinajpur district. These statues appear to have been made of black stone in the tenth-eleventh centuries. A magnificent image of Tirthankara Rishabhath has been found in *Subohara* village under the Dinajpur district. Another image was found from *Velo* village under *Kaharol* police station under Dinajpur district. The statue of Tirthankara Parsvanath was found in a village in *Khansama* of Dinajpur district.

From the beginning of the establishment of the empire most of North Bengal, or at least *Pundravardhanabhukti*, belonged to this empire. Due to the patronage of Brahmanical religion by the Gupta emperors, Brahmanical religion flourished during their reign. Therefore, the influence of Jainism which was observed in North Bengal in the pre-Gupta period came to a standstill in the Gupta period. Nevertheless, in this age, we can see some influence of Jainism in North Bengal.

Therefore, the religious activity was probably the first move towards Aryanisation in this remote area of India. Buddhism and Jainism in the beginning made the headway probably under the Maurya rulers. This was followed by a Brahmanical revival during the Gupta period. The Gupta kings also set up the tradition of land donations to Brahmanas and religious establishments which were followed by the Pala and Sena kings in later years to come. Whatever may be the royal religion, there usually remained a peaceful atmosphere in Pundravardhana in different periods.¹⁷

The influence of Jainism diminished during the reigns of the Buddhist Pala dynasty and the Brahmanical Sena dynasty. There is no written evidence or scriptural evidence about Jains in this age. However, some Jain images are announcing the existence of Jains. Nevertheless, the above Jain image also proves that Jainism had some influence in different parts of North Bengal during this period. It is thus seen that although Jainism did not gain royal patronage in North Bengal, it had its influence here from the time of its establishment. There is clear evidence of this effect until the Seventh century AD. This religion became extinct in North Bengal towards the end of the Pala period. Dr. Nihar Ranjan Roy estimates that all these *Digambaras Nigranthas* gradually became part of the *Siddha, Kapalika, Abadhuta* and other naked religions. Dr. Prabodh Chandra Bagchi also held a similar view.

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Ancient Jain Art and Antiquities of Tamil Nadu

Vijay Kumar Jain (Babaji)

35.Aruthangudi.

Ancient Jain Temple, Aruthangudi.Tiruvannamalai - Thiyagadurgam Rd, Sirupanaiyur, Tamil Nadu 605766 (11.959868, 79.082541) It is located at a distance from Tiruvannamalai 31kms and Kallakkurichi 40kms. Aruthangudi village in Villupuram district of Tamilnadu was the centre of attraction recently as it turned into a spot for discovery of idol said to be from the days of Cholas. The idol, said to be that of a Jain monk is located close to Ayyanar temple situated on the route connecting Manalurpettai with Thiyagaduruvam. It is about five-and-half feet in height and has a width of two-and-half feet, the sculpture has indicated that the idol belongs to the times of Cholas; This statue could have been a part of a larger temple built out of blackstone or brick during that time. As the time moved ahead, the shrine could have perished and this idol alone appears to have survived. The sculpture shows Jainism has flourished in the village during the time of Cholas, jains would have resided here who would have worshipped this sculpture. Though Jainism seems to be not active currently, it was active in the past. Further research could throw more light on presence of Jainism in this village and areas nearby.